

THE IMPACT OF SMOKING ON TRAINING AND PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT

KHALIMOVA DILRABO JALILOVNA

[*dilrabo.halimova@mail.ru*](mailto:dilrabo.halimova@mail.ru)

Kim Irina Leonidovna

[*irinakim30101987@gmail.com*](mailto:irinakim30101987@gmail.com)

Annotation: Physical exertion requires additional muscle regeneration and muscle cell growth. This is a natural reaction of the body. In smokers-athletes, the ability to use building materials in both processes is reduced. The result is indicated by weaker strength abilities, as well as much less noticeable achievements in training. Smoking also increases the production of myosin, a compound that affects the inhibition of muscle growth. After physical exercises, the muscles hardly recover. Moreover, during smoking, enzymes are produced that affect the breakdown of muscle proteins.

Smoking athletes may experience a deterioration in their physical condition. Cigarette smoke has an effect on hemoglobin modification. Hemoglobin is responsible for the transport of oxygen in the body. Oxygen plays a special role during long-term workouts or cardio workouts — thanks to this, all physical efforts will be effective.

Keywords: biochemical process, blood circulation, smoker accumulates

Prolonged and regular smoking has a significant impact on the functioning of the thyroid gland, larynx, pancreas, worsens digestive enzymes. Thyroid hormones have an anabolic effect (anabolism is a biochemical process in the human body, thanks to which new compounds are created at the molecular level. In simple words, it is the generation of cells and the synthesis of proteins and hormones, thanks to which the growth of muscle fibers occurs, which all athletes achieve).

Even at moderate loads, athletes who abuse smoking face a lack of oxygen. This is Shortness of breath is observed in smokers already at the beginning of the

lesson. A lot depends on the type of activity, but a person will not be able to run, jump, perform exercises that require a long time to maintain one pace of breathing. At the beginning of training, blood circulation accelerates, breathing becomes more frequent, the intensity of gas exchange increases – this is how the body reacts to the increased need for oxygen.

For fans of smoking, the heart works in an enhanced mode even without sports, there is increased blood pressure, and the vessels are spasmed, i.e. oxygen cannot flow to the tissues in the right volume. Athletes who combine smoking and sports increase the load on the heart and other organs, thereby ruining their physical fitness, and most importantly, health.

Based on the above, we present the main consequences of combining sports and smoking:

- decrease in the effectiveness of training;
- increasing the duration of muscle building;
- increased heart rate, occurrence of arrhythmia and tachycardia attacks;
- development of hypoxia due to lack of oxygen;
- dehydration of the body;
- possible loss of consciousness;
- increased risk of injury, because calcium is destroyed by nicotine;
- the appearance of shortness of breath after activity.

Like any bad habit, smoking will not be useful either for an athlete or for a person far from physical exertion. Cigarette consumption has a negative effect on health, and it is difficult to call such an addiction part of a healthy lifestyle.

If you want to see what the oral mucosa, bronchi, trachea and lungs look like after each cigarette you smoke, gut the cigarette butt filter. What you will see inside is only 1% of what a smoker accumulates inside his body for years. After all, this terrible coating of resins does not disappear anywhere. It only gets deeper into the tissues, gets into the blood, has an effect on the cellular level. And there are no safe cigarettes — weak, light, ultrathin. All these are marketing tricks that force weak-

willed "hostages" of the habit to find another loophole for themselves so as not to quit smoking.

To assess the harm of addiction, let's start small — with the appearance of a person. Modern people assign a huge role to external data. Girls, boys, women, men, regardless of age, social status and worldview, want to look decent and attractive. However, being beautiful means not only being well—groomed, but also healthy! No beauty salon will help fix what a smoker has been doing to himself for years. In short, the result of smoking is:

- flabby skin of an unnatural shade;
- yellow plaque on teeth and fingertips;
- brittle dull hair;
- lip deformity caused by constant cigarette holding;
- appropriate facial expressions.

Get closer to the smoker. Already at a distance of a meter, you can feel an incredibly repulsive smell. Tobacco smoke eats into the skin, hair. A persistent, never decreasing amber is formed in the smoker's mouth. Talking to such a person is unpleasant. You will hardly want to touch or kiss him. But avid smokers often become young girls and boys who have the construction of sensual relationships and the creation of a family in the future.

Literatures:

1. Боль в спине: разработка алгоритмов диагностики и лечения на уровне первичной медико-санитарной помощи Республики Узбекистан Авторы: Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна DOI: 10.37200 / IJPR / V24I6 / PR260396 Страницы: 4132-413

2. АНАЛИЗ РАЗРАБОТКИ ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИХ АЛГОРИТМОВ В СОЮЗЕ ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна JCR. 2020; 7 (5): 848-849

3. Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна, «АЛГОРИТМЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛИ В СПИНЕ», JournalNX - Многопрофильный рецензируемый журнал, IOCRТТА-2020, ISSN: 2581-4230, стр. № 47-51